

ACADEMICIAN NAIM KARIMOV'S LITERARY-AESTHETIC VIEWS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENCE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012867>

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Abstract.

In this small scientific article, academic scientist Naim Karimov's comments on the research of 20th century literature, writer Abdulla Qadiri's work, and his thoughts on his family are discussed. At the same time, the acknowledgments given to the scientist by contemporary literary scholars have been comparatively studied.

Key words.

literary dictionary, 20th century literary studies, literary-aesthetic views, scientific laboratory, literary-cultural phenomenon.

20th century Uzbek literary studies, especially criticism, has a special place in the history of literary and aesthetic thought. One of the most important issues is the scientific justification of the scientific researches of literary scholars, which have been influencing the literary process, and the literary-artistic features that distinguish them from each other. The scientific heritage of Naim Karimov, an academic scientist with many years of experience in a scientific laboratory, is also being regularly researched by scientists. This, in turn, determines the artistic value of the scientist's works. The research of Naim Karimov's scientific activities and works, study of his literary and aesthetic views, systematic analysis of the content of the scientist's scientific works are of particular importance in the development of the field.

Fundamental studies such as "Views of the 20th Century Literature" (2008), "The Causes and Factors of the Origin of the Great Massacre" (2014), "Literature and the Historical Process" (2013) serve the development of the field and provide a complete overview of the literary historical process. In particular, the encyclopedia "Abdullah Qadiri's contemporaries" created by the scientist in recent years is

important in enriching the science of literary studies with its clear characteristics.

This encyclopedia is an encyclopedic work that gives complete information about Abdulla Qadiri. Therefore, academician Naim Karimov was awarded the State Prize for this work on December 12, 2022, according to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "The volume of the book is so large that one cannot believe that it was written not by the scientific staff of an entire institute, but by a scientist who is condemning his ninety years of age. This book is a great innovation in studying and researching the life and work of our great writer Abdulla Qadiri, and opened a new front in the analysis of the writer's work. It contains a lot of information about the writer's friends, contemporaries, and comrades. It is not just summarized, it is stated in a very simple, scientific language [3;32]. Before this work, a number of scholarly articles on the work of Abdulla Qadiri were published in the press [5]. In the interpretations of his scientific articles, the opinions and conversations of Qadiri's relatives about his family and school education are presented. These data paved the way for the new work.

Naim Karimov chooses a writer-creator as a literary hero in each of his special works. His characteristic aspect is that the scientist evaluates the creator as a literary and cultural phenomenon of the Uzbek people. The researches and researches about Abdullah Qadiri also show the place and importance of our great grandfather in the history of Uzbek literature, the fact that his main works have been translated not only into Turkish, but also foreign languages, and the work of Qadiri scholars. Due to the fact that he is constantly studying and serving as a source for works of art, the scientist Abdulla Qadiri decided to restore the thoughts and realities of life of his contemporaries. The work introduces the historical period in which Qadiri lived and created, the emergence of national novels in Uzbek literature and his contribution to the development of the literature of the peoples of Central Asia, the creative ties between the writer and his teachers, family members, contemporaries and followers, and the writer's illuminates the spiritual world. In addition, the series of articles of the master scientist gives an artistic gloss to literary realities.

N. Karimov's article "Abdullah Kadiri himself, his contemporaries, and his contemporaries", the scientist connects the year of Kadiri's birth with 1897 and mentions that it was 1894 in the known scientific literature. The reason for discussion and reflection on this issue is Qadiri's own known opinion and written sources. "I don't know what year and month I was born. In any case, I was born in a poor, gardening family. At the beginning, I didn't know whether I was born in a rich family or in a poor family, but when I reached the age of 7-8, I knew for sure

from the fact that my stomach was not full of food and I did not see better clothes, that the throat of five souls is only one of 80 years old. as it comes from my old father's work, 1300 sarjins from the garden's harvest in the summer"[6]. So, relying on these opinions , the scientist examines the opinions of the writer's contemporaries and writers who wrote about the writer and gives this conclusion. As it is known from the words above, the writer himself did not know what year and month he was born. Habibulla Qadiri, the eldest child, based on his father's words that "according to the words of my relatives, I was born in the year of the accession of Emperor Nicholas to the throne", wrote 1894 as the date of birth of the writer. But "Uzbek bourgeois literature" published for the 6th grade of secondary schools . According to Professor A. Sa'di , the author of the textbook "XIX and XX Centuries" , A. Qadiri was born in 1897. If we take into account that A. Saadi had a conversation with the writer while writing this textbook and determined the dates of his life with the determination characteristic of Tatar scholars, it turns out that Qadiri was born in 1897" [6].

Abdulla Qadiri's works found their readers as well as their critics. We know that the highly talented Abdulla Qadiri was one of the first to be criticized by Mikhail Shverdin in 1928 with his article "The First Uzbek Novel". the tone of approach and advice is strong. However, he tries to adapt the novel to modern politics and to find "ideological errors" in the novel.

Literary scholar M. Koshjanov in his book "Qadri - a victim of tyranny", published in 1992, dwells on the places in M. Sheverdin's article that show some unscientific vulgar socialism vices. conduct, in general, it is noticeable that a certain goal was intended for the publication of this article. The main issue was to give an ideological assessment to the first Uzbek novel, and even connect this assessment to political views. [4;7]. Although M.Shverdin denied the novel as "ideologically foreign to us", he felt that the novel "has a great artistic value" [1;17]. Academic scientist N. Karimov comments on his creative excellence: "Abdullah Qadiri, like some of his contemporaries, did not study at the "Oliya" madrasa, nor at Sarbonna University. But the two novels he wrote have been loved as one of the masterpieces of Uzbek literature for over eighty years.[7]. In this regard, another opinion of the scientist about Qadiri should be stated: " Grandpa Qadir and his friends who have seen the world heard amazing "romantic" stories, read Jadid newspapers and magazines. But all of these serve as "building materials" for the writer... Raising the prototype to the level of a literary hero, sorting events, taking the selected ones to the degree of art, taking the image in different ways based on the essence of the event and the character's situation, and when necessary, it should be waved, so that

the reader will be shocked when he reaches this point " [8]. In Qadiri's works, the above-mentioned feature was predominant.

Naim Karimov is an encyclopedist who studied the undiscovered aspects of history from a literary point of view. His works, which are included in the content of his work, acquired a special meaning during the years of independence. In particular, finding the historical place of the literary truths of unstudied or forbidden creators requires the patient work of a scientist, the difficulty of consistently studying the evidence. Scientist I.Gofurov thinks about this. "He can be called an independent scientist with a full mouth. During these years, he became a doctor of science, one by one he created works that were in harmony with the content and demands of independence. He was ready for independence. All his creative plans were given an independent wing. The congratulatory voices of those who fought and gave their lives for independence kept echoing in his chest. Like many writers and scientists, Naim Karimov was reborn. Independence made him a great scholar, gave him the rank of academician. Wide great horizons opened. Thanks to independence, the great modern literature took an unprecedented path of development, freedom and independence took their foundations from them" [2;9]. Regarding the scientist's contribution to the field of literary history, Jabbor Eshankul expresses the following points. During this work, the scientist was not only the first in the history of our literature to get acquainted with the unfinished works of the writer, but also had the good fortune to study them deeply and comprehensively... Especially the enlightening novels "Cholpon" and "Maqsud Sheikhzade", Abdulla Qadiri's research on the life and work of these writers, in addition to opening new pages in our literature on the study of the life and work of these writers, is the first step in the world of Uzbek literature of not only scientific, but artistic scientific thinking about the life and work of great word artists. she was one of the beautiful nanunas who do not fall short of their standards", he gave a high assessment. "[3;30] . Khurshid Dostmuhammad admits that awareness of the original process-reality in literary studies is a characteristic of N. Karimov's personality." For example, what is the main feature that distinguishes this scientist from all other predecessors, that ensures his absolute uniqueness? In my opinion, the main feature is the awareness of the original processes that took place in the reality of Uzbek literature for more than a century ! In this place, the word "informative" is used in a very broad sense. To hold the primary documents with one's own hands and carefully examine with one's own eyes, to compare and analyze information, facts and figures, first of all, a great scientific potential is needed, and secondly, Sitting with one's head over the pages, where the dear souls

of various figures are screaming without him, the blood stains have not faded, it requires strong will, endless perseverance, and endless patience from a person [9; 12].

The comprehensiveness of Naim Karimov's scientific heritage and the credibility of scientific discussion topics determine the significance of the scientist's research. The scientist worked in all areas serving the development of society. Literary scientist Y. Solijonov also acknowledges this. "Naim Karimov is a comprehensive scientist. From his scientific heritage, not only literary studies, but also all types of art - theater, cinema, visual arts, music, as well as many fields such as history, pedagogy, psychology, ethnography, linguistics, and contributed to their development . it is possible to obtain the necessary information on the activities of our great-grandfathers "[10;20].

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